

Relationship between Factors Affecting Learning Social Studies and Academic Achievement among Secondary School Students in Coimbatore District

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ABSTRACT

Social study as a subject becomes a priority area in education, a right attitude towards the subject is the greatest need of the hour. A favourable attitude towards any subject helps the students to learn the subject interestingly and they score good marks. Attitude is one of the important factor that correlates with academic achievement. Study involvement is positively related to student achievement. It is necessary to determine the study involvement among students to understand and guide them. One major factor that facilitates study involvement is the emotional balance the student possesses. The investigator is interested in finding out the learning difficulties faced by students of secondary level in Social study in relation to certain psychological factors such as self concept and locus of control and certain educational factors such as attitude towards learning Social study and study involvement. For the purpose, the investigator had deeply studied the common difficulties faced by secondary level students in Social study.

Keywords: Factors Affecting Learning Social Studies, academic achievement

INTRODUCTION

Social studies seeks to examine and understand communities, from the local to the global, their various heritages, physical systems, and the nature of citizenship within them. Students acquire a knowledge of key social studies concepts, including change, culture, environment, power, and the dynamics of the marketplace. They learn about Canada and the role of citizens in a democratic society within a culturally diverse and interdependent world. They also acquire skills of inquiry and communication through field studies and other research projects; through the use of maps, globes, and models; and through the

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consideration of various forms of historical evidence. Students apply these skills to develop an understanding of Indian identity and democratic values, to evaluate different points of view, and to examine information critically in order to solve problems and make decisions on issues that are relevant to their lives.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN FACTORS AFFECTING LEARNING SOCIAL STUDIES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN COIMBATORE DISTRICT "

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Jha (2015) conducted an experimental comparison of different methods of teaching high school social science. The study was designed to test experimentally the relative effectiveness of various methods of teaching social science. The experimental study was conducted on a sample of sixty students in class X in bankipur government girls high school, Patna. These students were regular students and they were selected out of a total number of 100 students in the class.

Again the sixty students were divided into three groups randomly. The first group was control group, second demonstration group and third activity group. The investigator taught all the groups after administering pretest. Only one group was taught in a day. To avoid fatigue every group was taught in the first period. Post test was administered at the end of the experiment. Analysis of covariance was employed to analyse the results. The difference was further examined by paired t test. The main finding of the study was that there was strong evidence in favour of activity based approach in teaching school social science in respect of acquisition of knowledge, application of the scientific knowledge and development of social skill.

Kumar (2016) carried out an experimental study of the relative effectiveness of three methods of instruction exposition method, programmed learning method and multimedia method in social science education. The main objectives of the study were to find out the relative effectiveness of the three methods of instruction, to study the relative retention in learning through the three methods. A 3x2 factorial design was employed. The social science

students of classes IX and X of two inter colleges formed the sample of the study. In all 180 students were divided into three groups of sixty each. The findings of the investigation were the multimedia was more effective than the programmed learning method or expository method, the programmed learning method was more effective than the expository method, retention in learning by the multimedia method was higher than the other two, retention in learning by the programmed learning group and the expository group was equal, there was no interaction between three methods of instruction and the levels of intelligence.

METHOD OF THE STUDY

The present study attempts to find out the factors affecting learning social studies and academic achievement of secondary school students. Since the problem is concerned with "Survey" type, the investigator has selected the normative survey method for conducting the study.

The word 'survey' indicates the gathering of the data regarding current conditions. The word "normative" is used because surveys are frequently made for the purpose of ascertaining which is the normal or typical condition or practice. "Normative Survey" is applied in order to suggest the two closely related aspects of study. The descriptive or normative survey method of educational research is very common. It is that method of investigation which attempts to describe and interpret what exists at present in the form of conditions, practices, processes, attitudes, beliefs etc. It is concerned with the phenomena that are typical of the normal conditions. It is an organized attempt to analyze, interpret, report the present status of social institution, group or area.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

Nine schools are selected through stratified random sampling technique. The sample for the present study consisted of 300 secondary school students in Coimbatore district. The students of both sexes coming from both rural and urban areas were included in the study.

TOOL USED IN THE STUDY

The data are essential for carrying out research investigation. The data are collected with the help of the special apparatus called as tools. The success of a research must be received by selecting a proper tool for the research. So, that the investigator used the following tool i.e. factors affecting learning social studies and academic achievement.

DATA COLLECTION

In Coimbatore district, the investigator selected three government schools, three government aided schools and three self-financed schools using stratified random sampling technique. A set of management students from each school was selected in a random manner. Thus the researcher used stratified random sampling technique for collection of data from the vast area of Coimbatore district.

THE STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES USED

Suitable descriptive and inferential statistical techniques were used in the interpretation of the data to draw to a more meaningful picture of results from the collected data in the present study from the following statistical measures were used.

- Mean
- Standard deviation

- 'T' test
- 'F' test

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

1. It is found that, the male student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school is found to be less than that of female student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school.
2. It is found that, the Tamil medium student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school is found to be almost same that of English medium student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school.
3. It is found that, the government, government aided and matriculation school student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school is found to be almost same.
4. It is found that, the rural area school student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school is found to be greater than that of urban area school student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school.
5. It is found that, the literate parents of Secondary school student's factors affecting learning social studies is found to be almost same that of illiterate parents of Secondary school student's factors affecting learning social studies.
6. It is found that, the Hindu, Christian and Muslim religions student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school is found to be almost same.
7. It is found that, the OC, BC, MBC and SC communities student's factors affecting learning social studies in Secondary school is found to be almost same.
8. It is found that, the male student's academic achievement in Secondary school is found to be less than that of female student's academic achievement in Secondary school.
9. It is found that, the Tamil medium student's academic achievement in Secondary school is found to be greater than that of English medium student's academic achievement in Secondary school.
10. It is found that, the government, government aided and matriculation school student's academic achievement in Secondary school is found to be almost same.
11. It is found that, the rural area school student's academic achievement in Secondary school is found to be almost same that of urban area school student's academic achievement in Secondary school.
12. It is found that, the literate parents of Secondary school student's academic achievement is found to be almost same that of illiterate parents of Secondary school student's academic achievement.
13. It is found that, the Hindu, Christian and Muslim religions student's academic achievement in Secondary school is found to be almost same.
14. It is found that, the OC, BC, MBC and SC communities student's academic achievement in Secondary school is found to be almost same.
15. It is found that, there is a relationship between factors affecting learning social studies and academic achievement in Secondary school.

CONCLUSION

Education is the process of socialization by preparing the child for getting ready to take up the responsibilities of adult life. Hence, it is sort of mental discipline for growth and self activity. Education is the transmission of life by living, through living and for living. The prime function of education is to draw the potentialities of the child and develop them to meet the challenging situations in life. Students have problems in understanding the concepts in Social study. Teachers must identify the difficulties among children, should adopt innovative methods and use new technologies in education. Teachers need to pay more attention in developing positive attitude towards Social study and create interest in learning Social study.

The attitude of Secondary school students towards factors affecting learning social studies and academic achievement students is found to be at the average level. The present investigation has shown that the factors affecting learning social studies and academic achievement of Secondary school male students is lower than female students mean score. Thus it could be concluded that teachers should motivate the male students in their instructional classes by providing guidance to enhance factors affecting learning social studies and academic achievement.

The purpose of the present investigation with reference to some selected variables of the study indicated significant difference and relationship among certain variables. The study may find some usefulness in the field of Social study education and the findings of the study may serve as data for future research.

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